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**INTERNATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY STANDARDS BOARD
AND INDIAN INFORMATION AND TECHNOLOGY INDUSTRY:
PRE AND POST PANDEMIC APPROACH TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE
MEASURES****HIREN J. JANI****(PHD PURSUING) MAHARAJA KRISHNAKUMARSINHJI BHAVNAGAR UNIVERSITY - BHAVNAGAR****ABSTRACT:**

International Sustainability Standards Board is a board setup by International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in the year 2021-22. The main intention to set up the board was to create proper set of standards of reporting for the corporate firms around the world, so the investor can make a proper investment decision for investing in such firm which contributes in environmental, social and sustainable approach. It is set as IFRS-S where, S stands for sustainability. When it comes to India, India has also been pro-active while adopting international reporting requirements. Indian security regulation board SEBI, shifted from Business Responsibility Reporting (BRR) to Business Responsibility and Sustainable Reporting (BRSR), it is mandatory for all top 1000 companies listed in Sensex and Nifty. In this paper, the brief overview of ISSB will be given and five companies listed in Both Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and National Stock Exchange (NSE) will be evaluated on sustainable measures pertaining to Information and Technology Industry. In the Information and Technology industry of India, many companies adopt sustainable reporting standards; in this paper those measures will be evaluated. Information and Technology industry has been significant contributor towards India's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), contributing roughly around more than 7% on annual basis. Such selected companies will be evaluated on the basis of their contribution towards sustainability before and after the pandemic situation.

KEYWORDS: SUSTAINABLE, GREEN, CLIMATE, REPORTING, PANDEMIC, IT INDUSTRY**INTRODUCTION:**

Sustainable approach has become crucial as the new emerging trends such as rising health issues in human body, rise of artificial intelligence and constant innovation In the world recent scenario, where pandemic taught many lessons to humans especially to government across the world and corporate firms, that to survive the next pandemic situation or any other natural disaster, sustainable approach has to be adopted, by adopting sustainability standards, many natural calamities can be easily avoided, and many countries such as United Kingdom, Swede, Denmark has proved that adopting such sustainable measures in policy making and corporate behaviour is necessary to grow wealth sustainably. Indian IT industry has also been taking many steps towards sustainable approach and the main theme of this paper is centred keeping in focus the selected IT companies' approach towards sustainability before and after CO-VID pandemic.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To give overview of ISSB and Indian SEBI's sustainability framework i.e. BRSR.
2. To check the pre and post pandemic approach of selected IT companies listed in both BSE and NSE.
3. To give humble opinions and suggestions from the study.

Research Methodology:

This study mainly includes the secondary data i.e. annual reports collected from website of BSE and article published in journal and news paper, it covers the period of four years divided in two parts Pre pandemic time (2018-19, 2019-20) and post pandemic time (2020-21,2021-22). The list of selected IT companies is as follows;

1. Tata Consultation Services (TCS).
2. Infosys.

3. Mphasis.
4. Oracle Financial Services Software.
5. Info Edge.

BRIEF: INTERNATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY STANDARDS BOARD

The board is an initiative of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), which was started 20 years ago. The newly established board seeks to find out the possible sustainability standards and proper policy requirements that may help the common investor to take the best investment decision.

The board will work along with International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), the newly constituted board is accepted by G-20 countries, it was urged by the high demand proper sustainable measure requirements, as the global scenario is on a path to witness upcoming unpredictable event, one that just recently passed, CO-VID pandemic, which gave the world's leaders and these world level organizations, that sustainability is not a voluntary thing that can be used for either marketing purposes or can be easily avoided. The climate related risks are getting closer day by day, and the board enthusiastically looks forward to help the investor to invest in those companies that will be prioritizing not only financial targets and wealth targets but also sustainability standards. The Board proposed a draft year ago and such was welcomed by the all member countries of G-20.

Considering the materiality concept the standards will have pragmatic and material aspects not only theoretical rather proper accounting approach is followed, so investors have proper statistical data on which, they can take a proper investment decision.

The board seeks the overall acceptance by member countries, along with mandatory requirements in the part of countries' policy formulation. As investors' interest is to be safeguarded and so as to give them proper investment decision, board sought the support of financial markets regulatory body of member countries.

DEFINITIONS:

- 1) **Sustainable:**
It can be understood that satisfying the needs of human kind, without compromising the current resources. (United Nations, 1987)
- 2) **Scope 1 emission:**
It can be understood by such emissions are included directly from company' operations. For example, company's vehicles, production of goods etc. (United States Environmental Protection Agency).
- 3) **Scope 2 emission:**
It can be understood by such emissions are included indirectly from company's operations. For example, waste generated and disposal of same, transportation of purchased goods, commutation of employees etc. (United States Environmental Protection Agency).
- 4) **Full Time Equivalent:**
Full time equivalent can be calculated by employees' working hours dividing with workweek hours of employees. (Society for Human Resource Management)
- 5) **Business Responsibility and Sustainability Report (BRSR):**
BRSR is a report, made mandatory by Securities Exchange Board of India (SEBI), for 1000 listed companies in both Indian stock exchanges, to report sustainable measures adopted by companies, comprising into main nine principles. (Taxguru, 2022)
- 6) **Business Responsibility Report (BRR):**
BRR was introduced by SEBI for top 500 listed companies to give data about sustainability and corporate governance, in the last year it was replaced by BRSR. (Taxguru, 2020).
- 7) **Sustainable/ Green bonds:**
Sustainable or green bonds are used to help the environment, sustainable, or climate problem, where such finance is used to address the environmental issues or to conduct environmental projects. (World Economic Forum, 2022).

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Data Analysis:	PRE PANDEMIC		POST PANDEMIC	
	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22
TCS				
1) Use of Sustainable related words (in times)	19	28	70	98
2) Does company report GHG emission data?	YES	YES	YES	YES
3) Is scope 1 and 2 emission (FTE) has been reduced?	1.31	1.15	0.54	NA ¹
4) BRSR/BRR requirements	YES	YES	YES	YES
5) Issuance of Sustainable/Green bonds	NO	NO	NO	NO

TCS before pandemic situation, has been also practicing sustainable practices, but after pandemic, the company brought ground changing results, contributing more towards reducing carbon emission as well as green house gases.

Infosys	PRE PANDEMIC		POST PANDEMIC	
	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22
1) Use of Sustainable related words (in times)	39	48	58	116
2) Does company report GHG emission data?	YES	YES	YES	YES
3) Is scope 1 and 2 emission has been	1,24,770	1,39,407	77,351	60,682

¹ Due to pandemic situation FTE (Full Time Equivalent) data could not be gathered, as most of the employee conducted work from home.

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reduced?				
4) BRSR/BRR requirements	YES	YES	YES	YES
5) Issuance of Sustainable/Green bonds	NO	NO	NO	NO

Infosys on the other hand, also been practicing to contribute more towards sustainable behaviour, but after pandemic situation company focused more on sustainable approach. The company also follows to reduce carbon emission as well as green house gases.

PRE PANDEMIC

POST PANDEMIC

Mphasis	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22
1) Use of Sustainable related words (in times)	08	24	35	33
2) Does company report GHG emission data?	NO	YES	YES	YES
3) Is scope 1 and 2 emission has been reduced?	NA	37,259	19,061	18,155
4) BRSR/BRR requirements	NO	YES	YES	YES
5) Issuance of Sustainable/Green bonds	NO	NO	NO	NO

Mphasis before pandemic was somewhat contributing towards sustainable approach, but after the pandemic, it heavily contributes towards sustainability, its behaviour towards scope 1 and scope 2 reduction is quite significant, and must be appreciated.

PRE PANDEMIC

POST PANDEMIC

Oracle	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22

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1) Use of Sustainable related words (in times)	05	03	02	02
2) Does company report GHG emission data?	Data Not Available	Data Not Available	Data Not Available	Data Not Available
3) Is scope 1 and 2 emission has been reduced?	Data Not Available	Data Not Available	Data Not Available	Data Not Available
4) BRSR/BRR requirements	YES	YES	YES	YES
5) Issuance of Sustainable/Green bonds	NO	NO	NO	NO

Oracle Company follows sustainable practices, by adopting BRR requirements.

PRE PANDEMIC

POST PANDEMIC

Info. Edge	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22
1) Use of Sustainable related words (in times)	26	18	29	29
2) Does company report GHG emission data?	NOT APPLICABLE	NOT APPLICABLE	NOT APPLICABLE	NOT APPLICABLE
3) Is scope 1 and 2 emission has been reduced?	NOT APPLICABLE	NOT APPLICABLE	NOT APPLICABLE	NOT APPLICABLE
4) BRSR/BRR requirements	YES	YES	YES	YES

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5) Issuance of Sustainable/Green bonds	NO	NO	NO	NO
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Info. Edge company follows sustainable practices, by adopting BRR requirements.

FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

Findings:

1. Out of five selected companies, it is found that Tata Consultancy Services and Infosys has been consistent providing sustainable data even before pandemic situation and government regulations.
2. All the selected companies have started using sustainability related words after pandemic period such words include sustainable, green and climate etc.
3. Tata Consultancy Services, Infosys and Mphasis have been practising towards reduction in carbon emission and green house gas emission.
4. Every selected company follows either BRSR (Business Responsibility and Sustainability Report) or BRR (Business Responsibility Report) requirements.
5. None out of selected has ever issued either sustainable or green bonds.

Suggestions:

The research paper was conducted to give a brief about ISSB and Indian IT industry's approach towards sustainability before and after pandemic situation. It is analysed that out of selected companies (due to lack of proper policy guidelines), 'Uniformity' in reporting standards has not been observed, for instance some selected companies are showing scope 1 and scope 2 emission data in terms of Full time equivalent and some companies were showing that figures in respect of monetary terms (In Rupees, Dollars).

CONCLUSION:

International sustainability standards board can bring new policies, and is capable to make grass root changes in current situation of sustainable approach. To help such board, every country across the world should participate in taking sustainable measures by adopting board's suggested answers. Also the principle of uniformity should also be adopted so as to make comparative study.

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